

Postpartum Ovarian Vein Thrombosis: Case Report and Literature Review

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Abstract

Background: Postpartum ovarian vein thrombosis (POVT) is a rare but potentially severe complication. Its nonspecific clinical presentation may mimic other abdominal emergencies, delay diagnosis and increase the risk of serious complications, including extension to the inferior vena cava and pulmonary embolism.

Case Report: We report a case of a 28-year-old woman, second gestation and primiparous in her first delivery, who presented with acute right iliac fossa pain and fever on postpartum day 13 following a cesarean section. Laboratory findings showed leukocytosis and elevated C-reactive protein. Initial ultrasound was unremarkable, while contrast-enhanced abdominopelvic CT confirmed thrombosis of the right ovarian vein. The patient was treated with therapeutic anticoagulation (enoxaparin 1 mg/kg twice daily), resulting in complete resolution of symptoms within 48 hours. Thrombophilia workup was negative.

Conclusion: Postpartum ovarian vein thrombosis can be presented with a misleading clinical picture. Prompt clinical suspicion and imaging are essential. Early anticoagulation prevents thrombus extension and pulmonary embolism, reducing the risk of severe complications.

Introduction

Ovarian vein thrombosis (OVT) is a rare postpartum complication, with an incidence ranging from 0.05% to 0.18% [1]. It typically occurs within the first two weeks after delivery and predominantly affects the right ovarian vein in 80–90% of cases [2,3].

Clinically, OVT manifests as acute abdominal pain, often associated with fever, and sometimes with a palpable mass or peritoneal signs. This nonspecific presentation can be mistaken for other postpartum abdominal emergencies, such as appendicitis, pyelonephritis, adnexal torsion, or pelvic infections, which often delays diagnosis [4–7].

Without early management, OVT may progress to severe complications, including thrombus extension to

the inferior vena cava, pulmonary embolism, or sepsis, potentially jeopardizing the patient's life [6,8]. Diagnosis relies on imaging: contrast-enhanced abdominopelvic CT is the gold standard, while MRI is an alternative in case of contraindications or in young patients [9,10].

The objective of this report is to present a postpartum OVT case and provide an updated literature review to raise clinician awareness for early recognition and appropriate management of this rare but potentially life-threatening condition.

Case Report

A 28-year-old woman, second gestation and primiparous in her first delivery, delivered a female infant weighing 4600 g at 39 weeks of gestation via

More Information

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cesarean section. She presented on postpartum day 13 with acute pelvic pain. She had no relevant medical, surgical, or obstetric history. Immediate postpartum course was uneventful, and she was discharged on day 2.

On admission, she reported localized right iliac fossa pain and fever of 38.5 °C, without digestive or urinary symptoms. Examination revealed a clean cesarean wound, soft abdomen with focal tenderness in the right iliac fossa, a well-involuted and non-tender uterus, and no lateral uterine mass or abnormal lochia.

Laboratory tests showed leukocytosis (19,000/mm³) and elevated C-reactive protein (250 mg/L). Urinalysis

and vaginal cultures were normal. Initial abdominopelvic ultrasound was unremarkable. Given high suspicion for appendicitis, a contrast-enhanced abdominopelvic CT was performed, revealing thrombosis of the right ovarian vein extending to the inferior vena cava, without ipsilateral urinary tract dilatation (Figure 1).

The patient was transferred to the cardiology department and started on therapeutic anticoagulation with enoxaparin (1 mg/kg twice daily), leading to complete resolution of pain and fever within 48 hours. Thrombophilia screening was negative.

Figure 1: Axial CT Image Showing Thrombosis of the Right Ovarian Vein

Discussion

Postpartum ovarian vein thrombosis (POVT) is rare. Its pathophysiology is explained by Virchow's triad: persistent postpartum hypercoagulability, venous stasis due to ovarian vein dilation and compression, and endothelial injury associated with surgery or uterine infection.

The right-sided predominance of OVT is attributed to venous anatomy and uterine compression [7,9]. POVT mainly occurs within the first ten days postpartum, especially after cesarean delivery [2,3].

The clinical presentation is often misleading, with febrile abdominal or pelvic pain and sometimes digestive symptoms, delaying diagnosis and frequently prompting evaluation for other surgical or infectious emergencies such as appendicitis, pyelonephritis, or endometritis [5,6,8].

Imaging is key for diagnosis. Doppler ultrasound is simple and non-invasive but has limited sensitivity [10]. CT remains the gold standard with nearly 100% sensitivity, allowing evaluation of thrombus extension and exclusion of differential diagnoses. MRI is an

alternative if iodinated contrast is contraindicated [11,12].

Management relies on therapeutic anticoagulation, generally with low-molecular-weight heparin. Our patient received enoxaparin 1 mg/kg twice daily, with rapid symptom resolution, confirming the efficacy and safety of this approach [13,6].

Preventing severe complications, particularly pulmonary embolism (reported in 13–33% of cases and potentially fatal), remains a primary concern [14]. Therefore, in any postpartum febrile abdominal pain, OVT should be considered, with prompt imaging and initiation of anticoagulation.

Conclusion

Postpartum ovarian vein thrombosis is rare and often presents with nonspecific symptoms. High clinical suspicion and prompt CT or MRI are essential for diagnosis. Early anticoagulation prevents thrombus extension and pulmonary embolism, reducing the risk of serious complications. This case highlights the importance of systematic vigilance in postpartum patients, even in the absence of identifiable risk factors, to ensure rapid diagnosis and effective management.

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None.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Ethics Statement

The study was conducted in accordance with ethical and professional principles.

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